

PHRASEOLOGY OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

The article discusses the concepts of phraseology, characteristics, classification of these expressions both in general and specifically within the framework of understanding similar constructions in English language.

Key words: phraseology, phraseological units, phraseological combinations, phraseological seam.

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In any language there is a special layer of vocabulary consisting of stable, eloquent expressions. English is no exception. Such a layer called phraseology. In this article we will try to give a brief description such a phenomenon in language as a phraseological unit, to understand how best to implement translation of such phrases and explain the role of such constructions in the language.

Often, when translating phraseological units, difficulties arise, since the phraseological unit must be translated as an integral indivisible unit - the sum of the values of the units, but not as separate words. So, when using fixed expressions, it is not advisable to remove words, change the word order in them, replace or add words so as not to lose true meaning.

Thus, Phraseologism, -a.m. In linguistics: stable expression with independent meaning, close to idiomatic.

Phraseology, -i, ac. 1. Branch of linguistics - the science of phraseological units and idioms. 2. A set of phraseological units and idioms. language. 3. Beautiful, pompous phrases, hiding poverty or falsity of content (book) [1, 177].

When learning a language, it is important to have knowledge of its phraseology, since the use of such phrases in speech in itself enriches the language, makes speech more aesthetic, makes it easier to read fiction and journalistic literature on foreign language. Of course, the highest percentage of phraseological units of any language is contained in fiction. It is important to study this layer in order to understand the essence of the language, analyze ways of its enrichment and modernization (in this case, for example, replenishment by borrowing).

Thus, when studying English as a foreign language, phraseology presents a special problem when mastering, but, on the other hand, after studying and understanding this section makes it easier to understand English speech, express your thoughts and avoid literal translations of sentences.

In the process of developing phraseology, a problematic issue is often considered interaction of a phraseological unit with a word. On the one hand, phraseology is the equivalent of a word, but on the other hand we can talk about correlation phraseological combination and word. But to say that you can put a

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sign equality between a word and the phraseological unit with which it is identified, not worth it. A significant feature of a phraseological unit is its evaluation of what it expresses concepts, in turn, for the word evaluativeness is less significant. Thus, absolute identity between them is impossible. Moreover, if we talk about the structure itself words and phraseological units, then the word is a combination of morphemes, and phraseological unit is a combination of words. The word can be combined with other words, in unlike a phraseological unit, which is limited in this case - it is lexically stable and retains its constant composition.

It is logical that phraseological units are formed from free combinations of words, used in a figurative sense. Over time, such nominativity is erased and the expression is transformed into a stable construction. Thus, from the degree of erasure of the nominative meaning of the components of the phraseological unit, perhaps talk about a certain classification.

If we talk about the classification of phraseological units from the point of view semantic stability of their components, then according to V.V. Vinogradov [3,77], it is possible distinguish three types: phraseological combination, fusion, unity.

Let's consider phraseological fusions (from the Greek *idios* - own, characteristic) or, in other words, idioms are established combinations that are not subject to dismemberment, in which the meaning in combination does not depend on the meaning of the individual lexical units that make up a phraseological unit. For example, *be at smb.'s beck and call* - to be on errands, *at bay* - in a hopeless situation, and so on. In the given examples, it is necessary to note the fact that the concept of their imagery cannot be revealed without knowledge of historical features. This type of phraseological units is quite difficult translate into foreign languages, since in this case, the basic meanings of words, components of the given phraseological fusions were lost, and most importantly the meaning for them has become figurative. Phraseological conjunctions may include archaisms (that is, obsolete words, word meanings, phrases and other units language, displaced for some reason from active use by synonymous units <...>), they are characterized by special stability or impenetrability constructions of the phrase, the impossibility of changing the places of the constituent lexical phrases units.

It's time to consider phraseological unities - in this case the general figurative meaning can be traced, while at the same time preserving semantic separation of components. For example, *to paint the devil blacker than he is* - to thicken the colors, *to throw dust into smb.'s eyes* - to charm the teeth. To the characteristic features can be attributed to the special imagery of the combination, expressiveness, stability of the composition turnover, preservation of the semantics of individual components and the ability to combine with other phraseological units.

If we talk about phraseological combinations, then they are characterized by a certain semantic decomposability, approaching free combinations. Characteristics of this type of phraseological units is the possibility of free rearrangement of words, replacement one of the key lexical units included in the composition, a synonymous unit.

For example, *a pitched battle* - a fierce fight, or *a fierce battle* - a fierce fight (synonymous replacement of a key lexical unit).

Regarding the translation of phraseological units, one can note the particular complexity of this process, since it is difficult to convey in a foreign

language the same meaning, emotional coloring You can select partial ones (all is not gold that glitters (divergence in word order)); and full (to play with fire) equivalents in translation.

Accordingly, in order to produce an adequate translation, it is necessary to master various types of translation, that is, use descriptive translation, tracing, finding equivalents or analogues.

To summarize, we should talk about the grandeur of such a phenomenon of language as phraseology. In modern English, as, in principle, in other languages, there are a huge number of phraseological turns that enrich and make the language is more vivid, original and emotional. Moreover, the value is great phraseological turns from the point of view of regional studies, since in contact and subsequent study of a foreign language occurs a certain deepening in foreign language culture, history and even, perhaps, an understanding of the way of life and characteristics of foreign people's life being studied. In a word, studying the phraseology of a language - an integral part of its development, without which communication with foreign speakers' representatives will be quite difficult to carry out.

List of used literature:

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